

DAMAGE DETECTION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES BASED ON VIBRATION TESTING

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ABSTRACT

A new vibration testing method using a superposed waveform method (SWM) is firstly proposed as a fast, easy and universal vibration-based damage detection technique of structures. This method can be carried out conveniently over arbitrary frequency bands, especially in high frequency range, which is more sensitive to smaller damages. The SWM presented in this paper calculates the vibration parameters using the data of propagating waves in structures. By comparing the natural frequencies and mode shapes of a cantilever obtained by traditional vibration method and the SWM respectively, the reliability of SWM is validated in vibration analysis. In experimental studies, the location of impact damage in composite laminates is identified based on the SWM. A set of piezoceramic patches (PZTs) were acted as actuators on the damaged composite laminate by low velocity impact, and measured the propagating wave data by a scanning laser Doppler vibrometer (SLDV) system. A modified exciting signal was selected to actuate the propagating wave, which can be used for calculating the frequency response function (FRF) and the operational deflection shapes (ODSs) at each frequency by SWM. Results demonstrated that the mode shapes of high frequency resonance can clearly show the damage area, and the local resonance of damage can be tested to identify the damage location. Therefore, the SWM proposed in this paper provides an efficient and effective process for vibration measurement, especially at high frequencies, and also can be used for damage detection in composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dynamic performances of structures under vibration are important for strength design and life evaluation of the structures. As a global structural measurement method, many vibration-based methods have been developed for damage detection by measuring the detectable changes of modal parameters (natural frequencies, modal damping, mode shapes, etc.) in structures [1]. With the rapid development of modern industry, high-performance composite materials are now widely presented in various engineering structures, such like aerospace, domestic industry etc. However, the damage detection in composite structure becomes critical as many catastrophes caused by the defects in materials. Although there are many vibration-based damage detection methods developed and used for detecting composite structures [2], the high frequency testing is difficult to be performed, which appear more sensitive to small damages. Ratcliffe [3] proposed a gapped smoothing method (GSM) for detecting the defects in beams, which only need the mode shape data obtained from damaged structures. Yoon et al. [4] extended the one dimensional GSM to two dimensional case, and indicated that the operational deflection shapes (ODSs) can also be used for damage detection, which could be more sensitive to defects with wide frequency band detecting, especially in high frequencies. Piezoceramic (PZT) patches are used as actuators for high frequency excitation [5], but the signals are comparative weak for exciting structures in wide frequency band, especially in high frequency testing. The ODSs at certain frequencies, instead of mode shapes, are usually measured for damage detection. This is a compromised method, which may lower the precision but is more efficient in testing. So, how

to excite a big structure in wide high frequency band with strong and stable response is a critical problem in damage detecting techniques.

In this paper, a new method for vibration measurement is proposed. The so called superposed waveform method (SWM) computes the vibration response using the propagating wave data. The advantage of SWM is that a series of stable vibration responses can be calculated with only one measurement of propagating wave. Furthermore, the frequency response function (FRF) can also be obtained in a wide frequency band, which contains wide modal information of structure. The SWM is validated by numerical study analysing the vibration properties of a cantilever beam, and also verified in an experimental test on a damaged composite laminate. With the help of SWM, we can obtain the FRFs of the composite laminate, and find that at a certain high frequency, the structure is excited into local resonance caused by the damage. Thus we can locate the damage visually by the local resonance shape.

2 THEORY

2.1 Superposed waveform method

An ODS is defined as the deflection shape of a structure excited at a certain frequency. More generally, an ODS is the structure of motions forced by any excitation. The response of an excited structure is an accumulation of stress waves propagating in the structure, including scattering and reflecting of waves. If the structure can be treated as a linear system, the deflection response signal at each point within the structure is a superposition of propagating waves. In particular, if the structure is a linear system actuated by a time-harmonic signal, the response signal at each point is a superposition of waves excited by a series of single period sinusoidal signals with different time delays. Thus the ODS information can be obtained through superposing the propagating wave signal excited by a single period harmonic signal. However, if we try to obtain other ODSs at different frequencies, many measurements would be required. In order to obtain ODSs at arbitrary frequencies, through careful consideration, a new signal with period T is selected as shown in Fig. 1 and defined as

$$g(t) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{T}t\right) \quad (t \in [0, T]) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 actuating signal

Then, the equivalent actuating signal superposed by $g(t)$ with any period T' can be written as

$$g'(t) = \begin{cases} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{T}t\right) + \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}(t+T')\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{T}(t+T')\right) & t \in [0, T-T'] \\ \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{T}t\right) & t \in [T-T', T'] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

in which $T' \in [T/2, T]$.

A continuous actuation signal can be constructed by concatenating successive repetitions of $g'(t)$ in Equation 2. Extracting the frequency components of this signal by Fourier transform reveals that the components are well concentrated in the corresponding frequency $1/T'$ when $T' \in [T/2, T]$, as

shown in Fig. 2, which plots the spectra of actuating signals with periods $T' = [4, 5, 6, 7, 8] \cdot \frac{T}{8}$, separately. Although there are some peaks at higher harmonics, their magnitudes are quite small and can be neglected.

Fig. 2 Equivalent actuating signal superposed with different period T'

Thus, the excitation signal $g(t)$ ($t \in [0, T]$) can be applied to the structure, and the response signal can be measured at each location. Then, after superposing the wave data by a certain period T' , the ODSs of the structure at arbitrary frequency $f' \in [1/T, 2/T]$ can be computed by the SWM. The Fourier transform of the superposed waveform is analyzed, and the amplitude at f' can be extracted. Therefore, the improved SWM can calculate ODSs of a stable vibration in any frequency f' ($f' = 1/T'$) from a single measurement of the wave signals excited by $g(t)$.

2.2 Frequency response function computed by SWM

We can obtain a series of ODSs at frequencies $f' \in [1/T, 2/T]$ by the improved SWM, as introduced in 2.2. The equivalent continuous actuating signal $G'(t)$ can be computed by superposing the original signal $g(t)$ with each respective period T' ($T' = 1/f'$). Thus, the frequency response functions (FRFs) of the structure within the frequency range $[1/T, 2/T]$ can be calculated. Here, the velocity response is used as an example. The relationship between the actuation and response signals is

$$\mathbf{V}(\omega) = \mathbf{H}^v(\omega)\mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad (3)$$

where ω ($\omega = 2\pi f$) is the angular frequency, $\mathbf{H}^v(\omega)$ is the velocity FRF matrix, and $\mathbf{V}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} v(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt$, $\mathbf{F}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G'(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt$, for velocity response $v(t)$ at frequency f calculated by the SWM. $v(t)$ and $G'(t)$ are both long-term continuous signals with period T' . Thus, by incrementally altering the superposed period T' , vibrational properties of the structure, such as natural frequencies, mode shapes, etc., can be acquired from the FRFs over a range of frequencies. Furthermore, if a signal $g(t)$ with a very short period T excites the structure, vibration behavior at high frequencies can be obtained, which is difficult to achieve by conventional vibration testing methods.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In this section, the vibration of a cantilever beam analyzed by the finite element program ANSYS is studied. Fig. 5 shows the 1 m long aluminum beam with a circular cross-section of 2 cm diameter, made of a material with a Young's modulus of 70 GPa, density of 2700 kg/m³, and Poisson's ratio of

0.3. The beam is divided into 100 sections using Beam 188 element in ANSYS program, and the left end is fixed in all six degrees of freedom to set the beam as a cantilever.

The natural frequencies and mode shapes were calculated directly by modal analysis by the finite element program. By radial symmetry, only vibration parallel to the y axis needs to be analyzed. Table 1 and Fig. 4 illustrate the first six natural frequencies and mode shapes of the beam.

Mode	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th
Frequency(Hz)	14.234	89.098	249.02	486.72	801.91	1193.1

Table 1. The first six mode frequencies of the beam

Fig. 4 The first six mode frequencies and mode shapes of the beam

Fig. 5 The cantilever beam and the actuating signal

We then calculated the vibration response of the cantilever beam using the SWM. Using the actuation signal $g(t)$ in Eq.1 with a 2.222 ms period, i.e., a frequency of 450 Hz, the cantilever beam was excited at the free end in the y direction. The wave signals are extracted from all nodes after calculating the wave propagation in 222.2 ms, i.e., over 100 periods. Using the SWM, the vibration response from 450 Hz to 900 Hz was obtained at frequency intervals of 0.2 Hz. The FRF in the frequency band 450 Hz-900 Hz was computed by Eq. 3; the magnitude of the FRF is plotted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Frequency response function from 450Hz to 900Hz

The wave signals are extracted from all nodes after calculating the wave propagation in 222.2 ms, i.e., over 100 periods. Using the SWM, the vibration response from 450 Hz to 900 Hz was obtained at frequency intervals of 0.2 Hz. The FRF in the frequency band 450 Hz-900 Hz was computed by Eq. 3; the magnitude of the FRF is plotted in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 ODSs at 486.4Hz and 801.0Hz by SWM

Comparing the ODSs in Fig. 7 to the corresponding ODSs in Fig.5, the ODSs at 486.4 Hz and 801.0 Hz computed by the SWM are exactly the 4th and 5th mode shapes. Furthermore, the cross-correlation coefficients of the 4th and 5th mode shapes in Fig. 5 and 7 are calculated, respectively, to verify the agreement between the SWM and traditional vibration testing. The cross-correlation coefficient is defined as

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N x_n y_n}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N x_n^2 \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N y_n^2}} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are vectors of N parameters, each. According to the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, $|\rho(x, y)| \leq 1$. When $|\rho(x, y)| = 1$, x is parallel to y , and when $|\rho(x, y)| = 0$, x is perpendicular to y . The cross correlation coefficients between the shapes at the two frequencies are 0.99999 and 0.99995 respectively, demonstrating the accuracy and precision of the SWM.

4 DAMAGE DETECTION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATE

A carbon fiber reinforced laminate with impact damage is considered in this section. The laminate is made of M40J carbon fiber and NCHM 6376 resin, in the ply arrangement $[45/90/-45/0]_{3S}$, and has dimensions of 195 mm×63 mm×4.7 mm. The specimen was stressed by a 30 kN unidirectional tension, and then impacted by a drop hammer on its surface to produce impact damage inside the specimen. The height of the drop hammer was adjusted to control the impact energy. There was no visible damage on the surface after the impact, but interior damage, such as delamination, could occur.

Detecting this kind of interior damage is crucial to evaluating the integrity of composite structures. Traditional damage detection methods based on vibration have trouble obtaining resonance or responses under high frequencies, which are most sensitive to small damages.

In order to excite vibrations in the specimen at high frequencies, a set of piezoceramic transducer (PZT) patches acted as actuators, which could generate enough energy and actuate different ODSs by controlling the phase difference of the actuating signal input into each patch. The PZT patches are made of P-51 and have dimensions of 20 mm×5 mm×0.7 mm, with center frequency of 73.0 kHz. Figure 17 shows the PZT array (10 patches were pasted on the end of each side surface) and the measured area. The specimen was supported by two strings (Fig. 8(a)), approximating laminate vibration under free boundary conditions. The actuation signal was generated by arbitrary function generator DG1022, and amplified by power amplifier KH7602. The period of actuating signal $g(t)$ was 25 μ s, corresponding to frequency 40 kHz (Fig. 8(c)). The experimental results revealed that the torsional modes were more sensitive for detection and localization of impact damage than the bending modes. Therefore, the torsional mode actuated by the PZT array was used for damage detection. The patches were divided into two groups, as illustrated in Fig. 8(b): group I is indicated by blue: 1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 19, 20, and group II by red: 4, 5, 6, 7, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18. Two opposite actuating signals, i.e., $g(t)$ and $-g(t)$ are input in the two PZT groups, respectively. In this study, a scanning laser Doppler vibrometer (SLDV) system, PSV-400, measured the response of the composite laminate. A surface area of 108 mm×54 mm (Fig. 8(b)) is measured at 109×55 scanning points, respectively. The interval between neighboring points is 1 mm, approximately.

Fig. 8 (a) Composite laminate with PZT patches in quasi-free boundary condition;
 (b) Schematic diagram of the laminate with the PZT patches array;
 (c) The actuating signal

The FRFs from 40 kHz to 80 kHz were calculated using Eq. 10 at intervals of 0.5 kHz, and the results are shown in Fig. 9(a). The FRFs (Fig. 9(a)) show a clear peak at 46.5 kHz, which indicates the natural frequency of the structure, according to the previous numerical analysis. The corresponding mode shape can also be obtained as plotted in Fig. 9(b). Moreover, the damage location is evident in Fig. 9(b) without any further data analysis, necessary. These results demonstrate that the vibration under high frequency is very sensitive to damages.

Fig. 9 (a) FRF of the composite laminate in frequency band from 40kHz to 80kHz; (b) the mode shape

Furthermore, a small peak occurred around 52.0 kHz in Fig. 9(a). In order to calculate the FRF more accurately, the FRFs in the frequency band from 50 kHz to 55 kHz at intervals of 0.1 kHz were reanalyzed and plotted in Fig. 10. The vibration response can be analyzed with sparse frequency interval at first, and then reanalyzed in a desired frequency band at a dense frequency interval. This is a significant advantage of the SWM that may highly improve the experimental efficiency.

Fig. 10 The accurate FRF of the composite laminate in frequency band from 50kHz to 55kHz

In Fig. 10, the FRF curve is smoother than in Fig. 9(a). The local peak is located at 52.2 kHz, and the relevant ODS is plotted in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11 ODS of the composite laminate at 52.2kHz (top view and oblique view)

In Fig. 11, the ODS at 52.2 kHz only has one distinct local apex at the damage location, which corresponds to the local resonance of the damage region. Thus, damage can be detected and located using the SWM. This result indicates that if a structure is excited at a certain frequency, the damaged

area may generate local resonance, which may greatly improve the efficiency and the precision of damage location measurement. In this experiment, only the data obtained from the damaged structure has been used. The baseline data of the intact structure was not required. Moreover, no damage locating algorithm was used. Compared to traditional impact excitation methods, the SWM produces a strong and stable response at any frequency through superposition. Therefore, the SWM is an effective method to locating local damage using a large frequency band.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The superposed waveform method proposed in this paper is a novel method for vibration response analysis that can compute the ODSs and FRF of a structure in a continuous frequency band. Numerical and experimental results show that the SWM is an efficient and effective method for damage detection. Arrays of PZT patches actuated composite laminate with impact damage by select modes, and the response signal was detected by a SLDV system and analyzed by the SWM. The experimental study illustrated that the SWM is very effective in high frequency analysis; moreover, it indicated that the FRF can be reanalyzed to any desired accuracy, limited only by measurement precision. This approach provides a new efficient method to obtain the ODSs of structures, especially at high frequencies, which are more sensitive to damage and are difficult to probe by traditional methods. The SWM located impact damage in a composite laminate by the ODSs at high frequencies, directly, and by local resonance of the damage.

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